

Duration of dormancy of varieties released by APAU, India.

Variety with indicated dormancy					
1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk
Puskala	Sowbhagya	Dhanya	Gowthami	Vasista	Gutti Akkulu
Hamsa	Prathibha	Lakshmi	Chaitanya	Kotha-	Kothamolokolukulu 72
Tella-Hamsa	Sona	Kakatiya	Vajram	Bayahunda	Kothamolokolukulu 74
	Mahsuri	Vamsi	Mahendra		
Rajendra	Pothana	Prabhath	Krishnaveni		Pinakini
Sathya	Saleema	Vijaya-Mahsuri			Tikkana
Badva		Nagavali			
Mahsuri		Lakshmi			
Mahsuri		Surekha			
		Samba -			
		Mahsuri			
		Swarna			

for 80% germination) was estimated by germination percentage.

Germination was tested weekly starting 1 wk after harvest, by sowing 100 seeds of each variety on a petri dish with four replications. Samples were maintained at a constant 30°C.

In general, long-duration varieties had longer seed dormancy (4-6 wk) than medium-duration varieties (2-3 wk) and short-duration varieties (1-2 wk) (see table). Exceptions are some long-duration varieties (Badva Mahsuri, Mahsuri, Sowbhagya, Prathibha, and Sona Mahsuri) that exhibited shorter dormancy (1-2 wk). ■

Effect of variety, nitrogen, and stubble height on ratoon rice yield

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Short-duration varieties ADT36, ASD16, and ADT37; N (75, 100, and 125 kg/ha), and 20- and 30-cm stubble height were tested in a split-plot design with three replications. The main crop followed recommended practices.

ADT37 had the highest ratoon crop grain yield, straw yield, and productive tillers and highest daily productivity (see table).

Nitrogen at 125 kg/ha gave significantly higher grain yield, straw yield,

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Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Days to maturity (no.)	Productivity (kg/d)
ADT36	2.5	2.5	8.7	77.4	32.3
ADT37	2.8	2.6	10.2	76.5	36.6
ASD16	2.2	2.3	8.5	89.4	24.6
LSD	0.1	0.1	1.2	2.3	-
75 kg N/ha	2.4	2.4	8.8	80.2	29.9
100 kg N/ha	2.5	2.5	9.1	81.1	30.8
125 kg N/ha	2.7	2.5	9.4	82.1	32.9
LSD (0.5)	0.1	0.1	ns	2.3	-
20-cm stubble	2.5	2.4	9.2	81.3	30.8
30-cm stubble	2.5	2.5	9.1	80.9	30.9
LSD	ns	ns	ns	ns	-

and daily productivity than 75 kg N/ha.

Stubble height had no effect on ratoon yields and productive tillers.

The high grain yield in ADT37 could be due to greater number of productive tillers. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Resistance of some rice varieties to sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is an increasingly serious disease of rice in the Yangtze River Basin, especially hybrid rice. In the search for resistance genes to transfer into commercial

Reaction ^a of varieties to ShB during 1987-89 in China.

Cultivar	Disease ratings (mean and SD) ^b			Average ^a
	1987	1988	1989	
Ta-poo-cho-z	1.43±0.389	0.46±0.190	1.35±0.293	1.08 a
Tetep	2.05±0.315	0.57±0.157	1.65±0.245	1.19 a
Guyanal	1.19±0.304	1.72±0.198	1.93±0.305	1.61 a
IET4699	2.47±0.249	0.49±0.153	2.53±0.233	1.72 ab
Ratna	1.92±0.283	0.98±0.222	2.58±0.287	1.83 ab
Jawa no. 14	2.51±0.214	0.74±0.153	2.50±0.292	1.93 ab
IR64	2.47±0.294	1.01±0.282	2.35±0.201	1.94 ab
Kataktara Da-2	2.9 ±0.206	0.96±0.240	2.51±0.180	2.12 ab
Mian-Hua-Tiao	2.96±0.227	1.58±0.218	2.90±0.200	2.48 ab
Ye-Dao	2.91±0.224	1.90±0.255	3.15±0.275	2.65 ab
P5275	2.85±0.304	2.16±0.335	3.01±0.401	2.67 ab
Nampungbyeo	2.78±0.316	2.15±0.279	3.21±0.248	2.71 ab
IR9752-71-3-2	4.24±0.411	3.76±0.327	4.56±0.309	4.22 b

^a 0 = no lesion, 5 = lesions extend to top sheath. ^b Mean of 10 random hills/treatment with 2 replications. ^c Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by new Duncan's multiple range test at the 1% level.